

Temperature, Medium, Metals and Ligand Structure Effects on the Stability of the Metal Complexes of certain Schiff Base Ligands derived from Ninhydrin and Isatin with some Substituted-hydrazines

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Stability constants of Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Cd^{II} and Mn^{II} complexes with some Schiff base ligands of isatin-semi- and -thiosemicarbazones, isatin-S-methylhydrazine carbodithioate and ninhydrin-semi- and -thiosemicarbazones have been determined potentiometrically in different ratios of aquo-organic solvent media (ethanol, acetone, dioxane, tetrahydrofuran, dimethylformamide) at ionic strength $\mu = 0.04 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KCl) and different temperatures. The acid dissociation constants of the ligands have been also determined under identical conditions. The results are discussed in terms of the molecular structure of the ligands, the solvent characteristics as well as the nature of central metal ion. The stability constant values increase with increasing organic solvent in the reaction medium and decrease at higher temperatures. Thermodynamic functions have been evaluated and discussed.

Ninhydrin and its related compounds are very useful analytical reagents¹. Isatins possess diverse biological activities². Sulphur-containing substituted-hydrazones also possess wide spectrum of biological activities^{3,4}, and in many cases, coordination of these compounds to the transition metal ions enhances their activity⁴. These findings stimulated our interest to study the effects of temperature, nature of the central metal ion, medium and structure of ligands on the stability of bivalent Mn, Co, Ni and Cd complexes of Schiff bases derived from ninhydrin and isatin with thiosemicarbazide, semicarbazide and S-methylhydrazinecarbodithioate.

- 1: R = NH₂, X = S
- 2: R = NH₂, X = O
- 3: R = SCH₃, X = S

- 4: R = NH₂, X = S
- 5: R = NH₂, X = O

Results and Discussion

The computation of the stability constants of the investigated metal complexes is based on the fact that

the pH measurements during titration of a solution of chelating agent with alkali in presence and in absence of metal ion could be used to calculate the free ligand exponent (pL) and the number of ligand molecules attached per metal ion ($\bar{n}$). The experimental formation curves were constructed by plotting $\bar{n}$ against pL. In the systems, the maximum $\bar{n}$ values were found to be 1.0 or 2.0 depicting the presence of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal : ligand complex species. The decrease in pH value for these chelates during complexation compared to the free ligand as determined by titration process, indicates that the mechanism of complexation is based on hydrogen ion liberation. Stability constants of these chelate have been calculated by average value and straight-line method. For the average value method, the stepwise stability constants β_1 or β_2 values of the 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 metal : ligand complexes respectively, were determined from the constructed $\bar{n}$ -pL formation curves, where at $\bar{n} = 0.5$, $pL = \beta_1 = \log K_1$ and at $\bar{n} = 1.5$ for $pL = \beta_2 = \log K_2$. For straight-line method, the formation constant β_1 can be calculated using the relation, $\beta_1 L = \bar{n} / (1 - \bar{n})$. Thus plot of $\bar{n} / (1 - \bar{n})$ vs L yields a straight-line passing through the origin with a slope equal to $\beta_1 = \log K_1$. To calculate $\log K_2$ of

1 : 2 metal : ligand complex species, the following equation was used

$$\frac{\bar{n}[\text{H}^+]}{(\bar{n}-1)} = K_1 K_2 \frac{(2-\bar{n})-K_1}{[\text{H}^+](\bar{n}-1)}$$

Plot of $\bar{n}[\text{H}^+]/(\bar{n}-1)$ against $(2-\bar{n})/[\text{H}^+](\bar{n}-1)$ gives straight-line with a slope of $K_1 K_2$ and an intercept of K_1 from which K_1 and K_2 can be deduced.

Effect of solvents : Effect of the selected organic solvents on the stability of the complexes was represented by Ni^{II}-isatin-thiosemicarbazone (1) complex in 60% (v/v) organic solvent (ethanol, acetone, dioxane, DMF, THF)-water, $\mu = 0.04 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KCl) at 30°. Stability constant values ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) for this system are presented in Table 1. It can be seen that the stability constant values increase according to the order : ethanol > acetone > dioxane > THF > DMF. It seems to go parallel with coordinating ability of the solvents. Thus one can conclude that the coordinating ability of the solvents may retard the ligand-metal interaction.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF ISATIN-THIOSEMICARBAZONI (1)-Ni^{II} COMPLEX IN SOLVENT-H₂O (v/v) AT 30°

Solvent	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
Ethanol	6.09	5.94
Acetone	5.70	5.65
Dioxane	5.41	5.25
THF	4.96	4.92
DMF	4.70	4.67

Effect of organic cosolvent-water ratio : Stability constants of isatin-thiosemicarbazone (1)-Ni^{II} complex in different medium ratios of 60, 70, 80% (v/v) dioxane-water at 30° have been determined and given in Table 2. The results show that both $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ increase with increasing dioxane content in the reaction medium. This could be due to the decrease in the dielectric constant of the bulk mixing solvent⁵.

Correlation between the basicity of ligands and the stability of complexes : The acid dissociation constants

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF ISATIN-THIOSEMICARBAZONI (1)-Ni^{II} COMPLEX IN DIOXANE-H₂O AT 30°

Dioxane %	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
60	5.41	5.25
70	5.90	5.72
80	6.15	6.05

($\text{p}K_a$) of the ligands (1-5) may be correlated to the stability constants of their Cd^{II} and Mn^{II} chelates ($\log K_c$) measured in 60% (v/v) ethanol-water at $\mu = 0.04 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KCl) and 30°. The linear relation between $\log K_c$ and $\text{p}K_a$ could be checked from the relation, $\log K_c = a \text{p}K_a + b$, where a and b are constants. The slopes (a) for Cd^{II} = 0.72 and for Mn^{II} = 0.50. This indicates that the modes of ligand bonding toward the metal ions are similar in these systems. Deviation from a slope of unity is mainly attributed to possible steric interactions to π -electron back-donation from the metal ion to the ligand or to structural changes in the ligand which alter the strength of the metal ion-donor atom bonds within the ligand.

Effect of nature of metal ion : Stability constants ($\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$) of complexes of isatin-thiosemicarbazone (1) and ninhydrin-thiosemicarbazone (4) Schiff base ligands with Ni^{II}, Co^I, Cd^I and Mn^I in 60% (v/v) ethanol-water at $\mu = 0.04 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KCl) and 30°, have been determined potentiometrically and the values are given in Table 3. The results reveal that the order of stability constants is Ni^I > Co^I > Cd^I > Mn^{II}, which is in good agreement with that found by

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES OF ISATIN- AND NINHYDRIN-THIOSEMICARBAZONES (1, 4) WITH DIFFERENT METALS IN 60% (v/v) ETHANOL-H₂O AT 30°

Complex	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
1-Ni ^{II}	6.09	5.94
1-Co ^{II}	5.95	5.55
1-Cd ^{II}	5.45	5.41
1-Mn ^{II}	4.48	-
4-Ni ^{II}	5.36	5.32
4-Co ^{II}	4.93	-
4-Cd ^{II}	4.67	-
4-Mn ^{II}	4.10	-

Mellor and Maley⁶ and Irving and Williams⁷. This sequence has also been reported by others⁸. The regularity of this stability sequence can be correlated with a monotonic decrease in the ionic radii⁹ and a monotonic increase in the second ionisation potential. Generally, in all the systems studied, the values of $\log K_1 > \log K_2$. This may be due to the fact that the interaction of the second molecule of the ligand is usually slower than the first one. This can be ascribed to the increase in the Lewis acidity of the free metal ion as compared to 1 : 1 chelated ion.

Effect of ligand structure : Dissociation constants (pK_a) of the ligands 1–5 and stability constants of their complexes with Mn^{II} and Cd^{II} in 60% (v/v) ethanol-water at $\mu = 0.04 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KCl) and 30°, have been determined potentiometrically (Table 4). The results reveal that the pK_a values for 4 and 5 are lower than that of 1 and 2. This may be due to the electron-attracting property of the two actual carbonyl groups of ninhydrin moiety. On the other hand, pK_a values of 2 and 5 are lower than that of 1 and 4. This may be due to the high electronegativity of oxygen atom compared to sulphur atom.

The data (Table 4) show that the stability constants

TABLE 4— pK_a VALUES FOR THE LIGANDS 1–5 AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THEIR Mn^{II} AND Cd^{II} COMPLEXES IN 60% (v/v) EtOH– H_2O AT 30°

Complex	pK_a	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$
	9.30		
1- Mn^{II}		4.48	–
1- Cd^{II}		5.45	5.41
	9.00		
2- Mn^{II}		4.24	–
2- Cd^{II}		4.81	4.16
	7.50		
3- Mn^{II}		3.60	–
3- Cd^{II}		4.16	4.10
	8.33		
4- Mn^{II}		4.10	–
4- Cd^{II}		4.67	–
	8.03		
5- Mn^{II}		3.90	–
5- Cd^{II}		4.47	4.10

of Mn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes with ligands 1 and 4 are higher than those of the corresponding 2 and 5. This may be interpreted on the basis that the higher atomic size sulphur atom can donate its lone-pair electrons to the central metal ion easily than oxygen atom. Thus one may conclude that the M–S bond may be somewhat stronger as compared to M–O bond. In addition, the stability constants of Mn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes of ligands 1 and 2 are higher than those of the corresponding ninhydrin ones. This result can be ascribed to electron-attracting property of the two actual groups of ninhydrin moiety which can weaken the M–O and M–S bonds.

Temperature effect : Stability constant of Mn^{II} -isatin-thiosemicarbazide Schiff base (1) complex at different temperatures of 25, 30, 35 and 40° in 60% (v/v) ethanol-water at $\mu = 0.04 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KCl) has been determined. The value of enthalpy change ΔH° is calculated from the slope of the least-square line for a plot of $\log K$ vs $1/T$ according to the relation, $\log K = (-\Delta H^\circ/2.3 RT) + \text{constant}$. The free energy change (ΔG°) and the entropy change (ΔS°) are calculated at $T = 298 \text{ K}$ from the equations, $\Delta G^\circ = 2.3 RT \log K$ and $\Delta S^\circ = (\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ)/T$. Stability constant ($\log K$) values together with the thermodynamic functions are presented in Table 5. Stability constant values are found to be lower at higher temperatures. This suggests that

TABLE 5—STABILITY CONSTANT OF ISATINTHIOSEMICARBAZONE (1)- Mn^{II} COMPLEX IN 60% (v/v) ETHANOL- H_2O AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	$\log K_1$	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H^\circ$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\circ$ cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
25	4.68	6.42	16.73	34.60
30	4.48			
35	4.24			
40	4.10			

the investigated metal-ligand interaction is favoured at low temperature. The decrease in $\log K$ values with increase in temperature and negative ΔG° and ΔH° values indicate that the reaction of the system is exothermic and spontaneous.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade. The ligands

(1-5) were synthesised by the reported method¹⁰.

Stock solutions (0.1 mol dm⁻³) of the metal ions (NiCl₂.6H₂O, CoCl₂.6H₂O, CdCl₂.H₂O and MnCl₂.4H₂O) were prepared in double-distilled water; the exact concentrations determined by complexometric titration with EDTA. The requisite amount of each ligand was dissolved in the selected organic solvents (ethanol, acetone, dioxane, tetrahydrofurane THF and dimethylformamide DMF). A 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ NaOH solution was prepared in CO₂-free double-distilled water and standardised with potassium hydrogen phthalate. A 2.0 mol dm⁻³ stock solution of KCl was used as supporting electrolyte. Generally, dilute solutions were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock.

Determination of the formation constants: The formation constants of the five ligands (1-5) with bivalent Ni, Co, Cd and Mn were determined potentiometrically in different organic solvent-water mixtures in various proportions and at different temperatures by adopting the Irving and Rossotti pH-titration technique¹¹. pH was measured using an Accumet 825 MP pH meter and calibrated using two buffer solutions of pH 4.01 and 9.14.

All the titrations were performed by introducing 1 ml of the metal (10⁻² mol dm⁻³) + 5 ml of each Schiff base ligand (10⁻² mol dm⁻³) + 1 ml of KCl (2.0 mol dm⁻³), to the thermostated titration cell. The total volume was made upto 50 ml by adding water and the organic cosolvent to attain the desired medium composition. The mixture was titrated against standard NaOH solution in absence and in presence of metal ion to determine the dissociation constant of the ligand and its corresponding complex formation constant with the metal ion respectively, under identical conditions. The ionic strength was maintained at $\mu = 0.04$ mol dm⁻³ (KCl). Purified nitrogen gas was bubbled through the titrating solution to keep inert atmosphere and stirred magnetically. The pH-meter readings was corrected¹². The dissociation constants (pK_a) of the free ligands (1-5) and the stability constants (K) of their metal complexes were calculated by using the graphical method (average value method) and the linear plot method. The mean pK_a and $\log K$ values of these two

different calculation methods are listed in Tables 1-5.

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